

NLR AS DIAGNOSTIC VALUE FOR THE SEVERITY OF ACUTE CHOLANGITIS**Fuss Ju.,***Department of Surgery, St. Paraskeva medical center, Lviv, Ukraine***Voloboyeva A.,***Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care,
Communal Municipal Clinical Hospital 8, Lviv, Ukraine***Polovyj V.***Department of surgery, Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernovtsy, Ukraine***Abstract**

Acute cholangitis (AC) is a serious infectious condition in which systemic complications occur and can lead to mortality.

Methods: In the retrospective analyses, 411 patients who were followed at the 1st territorial medical association of Lviv, the medical center of St. Paraskeva, the emergency hospital of Chernivtsi between 2020 and 2024 and met the definitive diagnosis criteria for acute cholangitis according to the Tokyo guidelines 2018 were enrolled as the study group.

Results: There was a statistically significant correlation between the severity of cholangitis and the degree of lymphocytopenia.

Conclusions: The increase in the severity of cholangitis caused an increase in NLR and PLR and a decrease in lymphocyte count. Regarding these fact, we assume that lymphocyte count and NLR might have a predictive value on this disease severity of acute cholangitis. We recommended the use of lymphocyte count for grading acute cholangitis severity and providing early biliary drainage in patients.

Keywords: acute cholangitis, complication, neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio.

INTRODUCTION. Acute cholangitis (AC), a severe inflammatory condition of the bile ducts, arises from biliary obstruction, leading to bile stasis and subsequent infection. This obstruction elevates intraductal pressure, facilitating the translocation of bacteria or endotoxins from the bile into the systemic circulation. The clinical presentation of AC spans a broad spectrum, from mild cases amenable to conservative management to severe instances culminating in septic shock [1,2]. Several studies have investigated predictors of AC severity, suggesting procalcitonin, presepsin and delta neutrophil index (DNI) as prognostic markers, but these cannot be performed routinely due to their high cost or dependence of specific analyzers [3]. There is a need for a new, inexpensive, and simple predictor of severe acute cholangitis, to stratify patients for urgent biliary drainage, close monitoring, and selective transfer to the intensive care unit (ICU) as early as possible. The neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) is reported to be predictive of adverse outcomes in acute pancreaticobiliary disease [4].

MATERIAL ANF METHODS. In the retrospective analyses, 411 patients who were followed at the 1st territorial medical association of Lviv, the medical center of St. Paraskeva, the emergency hospital of Chernivtsi between 2020 and 2024 and met the definitive diagnosis criteria for acute cholangitis according to the Tokyo guidelines 2018 were enrolled as the study group. In the same period 99 patients without AC who

had normal inflammatory markers and underwent endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) for choledocholithiasis, stent removal, or stent replacement were included in the study as a control group.

Patients age, gender, hemogram, CRP, severity and source of AC have been recorded from the hospital database. The patients were divided into groups as grade I (mild), grade II (moderate) and grade III (severe) acute cholangitis according to TG 18.

Continuous variables were reported as medians with interquartile ranges (IQR) for not normally distributed; categorical variables were expressed as numbers and percentages. Comparisons between groups for continuous variables were evaluated using the Kruskal–Wallis test and Mann–Whitney U test, and for categorical variables, Fisher’s exact test was used. Univariate logistic regression analysis and multivariate logistic regression with stepwise variable selection were used to analyze the relationship between organ dysfunction or predictors and IHM. Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS.

A total of 510 participants, including 411 cholangitis and 99 control group patients were included in this retrospective analysis. The distribution of demographic and clinical findings of the participants are given in Table 1

Table 1

Characteristic of patients with acute cholangitis				
Characteristics, (n=510)	Total (n=510)	Control (n=99)	Cholangitis (n=411)	p-Value
Age	71 (59-76)	76 (70-84)	74 (64-82)	<0.001
Male/female	289/221	65/34	225/186	0.123
Cholangitis severity				
Control	99	99	NA	<0.001
Mild	159	NA	159	<0.001
Moderate	108	NA	108	<0.001
Severe	144	NA	144	<0.001
<i>Laboratory data</i>				
WBC ($\times 1000/\mu\text{L}$)	9.7 (6.9–12.0)	7.5 (6.7-10.8)	16.2 (10.0–21.4)	<0.001
AST, U/L	109 (6.8-2.538)	27.6 (7-764)	134 (6.8-2.538)	<0.001
ALT, U/L	125.5 (2-1.486)	32 (2-899)	154 (5-1.497)	<0.001
INR	1.05 (1.00-1.10)	1 (0.9-2.6)	1.2 (1.05-1.21)	<0.001
Glucose (gm/dL)	115 (23-815)	99 (60-332)	120 (25-820)	<0.001
Creatinine (gm/dL)	0.82 (0.65-0.99)	0.76 (0.44-1.85)	1.13 (1.07-1.22)	<0.001
T-bilirubin (mg/dl)	5.7 \pm 4.6	1.2 \pm 4.4	6.2 \pm 4.5	<0.001
Neutrophil ($10^6/\text{L}$)	8.293 (515-51.132)	4.000 (531-10.555)	9..870 (1.365-52.250)	
Lymphocyte ($10^6/\text{L}$)	995 (80-10.000)	1.850 (950-3.800)	790 (90-10.000)	<0.001
NLR	9.5 (0.5-120)	2 (0.5-7.5)	14 (0.5-120)	<0.001
PLR	0.2 (0-4)	0.2 (0-0.5)	0.4 (0-4)	<0.001
Platelet ($10^9/\text{L}$)	250 (15-850)	280 (65-550)	220 (15-850)	<0.001

When the table was examined, no statistically significant relationship was found between the group in terms of individuals gender distribution. There was a statistically significant difference between the two group in all laboratory parameters ($p < 0.005$).

The results of Chi-square analysis evaluating whether there was a relationship between the cholangitis or control group and the degree of lymphocytopenia

of the participants were given in table II. When the table was examined, a statistically significant correlation was found between the patients in the cholangitis or control group and the degree of lymphocytopenia ($p < 0.005$). While most of the control group had a normal lymphocyte count, the majority of the cholangitis group had lymphocytopenia.

Table 2

Evaluation of the relationship between degree of lymphocytopenia and the study group				
Grade of lymphocytopenia	Study groups (n=411)			p
	Control (n=99)	Cholangitis (n=411)		
Normal	85 (85.9%)	132 (32.1%)		<0.001
Grade 1 (<800)	14 (14.1%)	85 (20.7%)		
Grade 2 (500-800)	0	98 (23.8%)		
Grade 3 (200-500)	0	74 (18%)		
Grade 4 (<200)	0	22 (5.4%)		
Grade of lymphocytopenia	Severity of cholangitis (n=411)			P
	Mild (n=159)	Moderate (n=108)	Severe (n=144)	
Normal	71 (44.6%)	39 (36.1%)	24 (16.7%)	<0.001
Grade 1 (<800)	41 (25.8%)	12 (11.1%)	15 (10.4%)	
Grade 2 (500-800)	27 (17%)	37 (34.2%)	59 (40.9%)	
Grade 3 (200-500)	19 (11.9%)	19 (17.6%)	45 (31.3%)	
Grade 4 (<200)	1 (0.7%)	1 (1%)	1 (0.7%)	

The results of the Chi-square analysis evaluating whether there was a relationship between the severity of cholangitis and the degree of lymphocytopenia of the patients were given in Table II. When the table was examined, a statistically significant relationship was found between the severity of cholangitis and the degree of lymphocytopenia (< 0.05). It was observed that as the disease severity increased, the proportion of patients with normal lymphocytopenia degree decreased, and abnormal findings increased.

The results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test, which evaluates whether there was a significant difference between the NLR and PLR results according to the severity of cholangitis, were given in Table III. When the table was examined, it was determined that there was a statistically significant difference between the NLR and PLR results according to the cholangitis severity of the patients (< 0.05).

Evaluation of patients NLR and PLR results by cholangitis severity

	Cholangitis	N	Median	Min-Max	p
NLR	Mild	159	7.53	0.95-59.65	<0.001
	Moderate	108	18.32	0.55-110.5	
	Severe	144	22.35	0.60-120.5	
PLR	Mild	159	0.19	0.05-4.12	<0.001
	Moderate	108	0.27	0.02-1.56	
	Severe	144	0.25	0.01-3.21	

It was seen that the NLR and PLR results of the patients increased at the severity of cholangitis increased. When the association between the correlation analysis and the severity of cholangitis and the results of NLR and PLR was examined, it was observed that there was a positive relationship in both ratios (<0.05). While the relationship between cholangitis severity and NLR was low ($r=0.418$).

As a result, it was determined that the increase in the severity of cholangitis caused an increase in the degree of lymphocytopenia, NLR, and PLR results. Although the increase in the degree of lymphocytopenia and NLR was considered statistically significant, the increase in PLR was not at an acceptable level.

DISCUSSION. Systemic inflammation is regulated via lymphocytes, and a decrease in their concentration caused disease progression. Inflammatory status in the body leads to lymphopenia, regarding this, it may be said that any fluctuation of NLR could elaborate the immuno-inflammatory changes in acute cholangitis [5,6].

In this study, it was determined that the degree of lymphocytopenia, NLR, and PLR of this patients increased as the severity of cholangitis increased. When the association between the relation analysis and the severity of cholangitis and the results of NLR and PLR was examined, it was observed that there was a positive relationship in both ratios ($p<0.05$). The initiation of antibiotherapy and biliary drainage at this early stage could provide a window of opportunity for the patient with severe acute cholangitis. There is a need for the designation of certain biomarkers to be used as predictive parameters. Lymphocyte count and NLR can be

used as cheaper markers and routinely measured in clinical practice.

CONCLUSION. The increase in the severity of cholangitis caused an increase in NLR and PLR and a decrease in lymphocyte count. Regarding these fact, we assume that lymphocyte count and NLR might have a predictive value on this disease severity of acute cholangitis. We recommended the use of lymphocyte count for grading acute cholangitis severity and providing early biliary drainage in patients.

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